

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

An IOC Newsletter on toxic algae and algal blooms

No. 19

A new “diablillo parasite” in the toxic Dinoflagellate *Alexandrium catenella* as a possibility to control harmful algal blooms

A red-tide of the paralytic shellfish poisoning producing dinoflagellate *Alexandrium catenella* was detected in the harbor of Tarragona (Catalonia, Spain) in June 1998, when monitoring noxious phytoplankton. During the microscopic enumeration of phytoplankton cells present in water samples, collected in the decline phase of the bloom, several unknown round cysts were present (Fig. 1) distinct from those of *Alexandrium* [1]. Water samples, maintained in culture flasks, showed that these cysts infected *A. catenella* cells, which subsequently released hundreds of flagellated

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Fig. 1. Light microscopy of “diablillo parasite” in living samples infecting *A. catenella*. **a**, View of a dark parasite cyst full of quiet swimmers. **b**, View of a parasite cyst during germination, containing inside about half of the total number of swimmers formed in this cyst; swimmers in very active movement. **c**, **d**, Two photos of the same parasite cyst in the final process of germination, containing about a dozen swimmers; a drop remains inside. **e**, Various parasite cysts and empty thecae of the dinoflagellate; one full dark cyst and 3 empty translucent cysts are apparent. **f**, Cluster of empty parasite cysts. Scale bars represents 5 μ m.

◆ New Zealand

A new species of *Gymnodinium* that caused the 1998 summer human respiratory syndrome and decimation of marine life in Wellington Harbour, New Zealand

Immediately after a series of fish and marine fauna kill episodes and outbreaks of human respiratory illness being reported off Wairarapa coast and Hawke Bay on the North Island east coast (Fig. 1) (Harmful Algae News 17: 1-5), Wellington Harbour experienced a

severe toxic outbreak that persisted from mid-February to April 1998. This was the first toxic outbreak ever to occur in the region and decimated almost all marine life (including seaweeds) in the harbour. During this unusual outbreak, eels and flounders were first noticed as

the major harbour kills, and then spread across to kills of other pelagic fish (e.g., yellow-eyed mullet, barracouta, mackerel, leather jacket, stargazers, and kaha-wai) and marine invertebrates (e.g., sea slug, starfish, sea urchin, and abalone).

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cells (Fig. 1b,c,d). Newly formed flagellates then infected other *A. catenella* cells. These results indicate the parasitic nature of the unknown cysts, which were given the name "diablillo parasites" (a Spanish word related with devil). The "diablillo parasite" was analyzed to reveal its possible effectiveness as a biological tool for controlling toxic algal blooms. Besides the parasite itself twelve strains of *A. catenella* were isolated from field samples and cultured for this purpose.

The new parasite

The flagellated cells and cysts remained non fluorescent with blue light excitation in light microscopy, hence lack chlorophyll pigments. Scanning electron microscopy images show morphological details of the parasite (Fig. 2).

The flagellates (Fig. 2a,b) are 3 μm long and 1.5 μm wide and possess two unequal flagella (of 8 μm and 2 μm length respectively). The long flagellum shows hairs over its full length, whereas the short one is naked. The cyst stage (Fig. 2c,d) is spherical and of variable diameter, depending on the size of the infected host cell (30-40 μm in *A. catenella*). Cysts show very small spiny protuberances on their surface and a variable number of pores (usually 2 to 7 pores, 2 μm of diameter) in their transparent walls. These pores are difficult to resolve with light microscopy. The wall of the cyst shows yellowish fluorescence when stained with calcofluor [2].

Life cycle of the parasite

During the reproductive cycle of the parasite, the swimmers infect the motile vegetative cells of *A. catenella*, but do

Table 1.- Species of phytoplankton infected experimentally with the "diablillo parasite". C, cultures; NP, natural population.

Species sensitive to infection

Alexandrium catenella C, NP.
Alexandrium minutum C, NP.
Alexandrium affine C.
Protoperdinium bipes NP.
Scrippsiella trochoidea C, NP.
Gymnodinium sanguineum C.
Prorocentrum micans NP.
Dinophysis sacculus NP.

Species resistant to infection:

Alexandrium taylori C.
Gyrodinium corsicum C.
Coscinodiscus cf. radiatus C.
Thalassiosira weissfloguii C.

Fig. 2. Scanning electron micrographs of the diablillo parasite infecting *A. catenella*, retained on polycarbonate filters. a, View of 8 swimmers. Scale bar 2 μm . b, View of a swimmer, showing long flagellum with hairs and short naked flagellum. Scale bar 2 μm . c, parasite cyst with protuberances on surface and the remaining empty theca of the infected dinoflagellate. Scale bar 10 μm . d, parasite cyst showing pores (3 in front view and 2 in side view) through which swimmers escapes from cyst. Scale bar 10 μm .

not infect non-motile cells. They first attach to the cingulum of the dinoflagellate, which subsequently stops its movement some hours later, and degradation of the hosts chloroplast becomes apparent (shown as a clear area usually located at the center of the host cytoplasm). During the following hours the clear area increases in size until it occupies the entire host cytoplasm 24 hours after infection. The parasite cyst is totally formed within 48 hours after infection and the theca of the dinoflagellate is disjoined. In undisturbed cultures cysts remained joined to empty thecae of the dinoflagellates (Fig. 2c).

One infected host usually develops only one parasite cyst, but occasionally several small cysts (2-5 cysts) were observed inside a single dinoflagellate cell. These observations possibly suggest multiple infections (various swimmers infecting the same cell). The parasite cysts are transparent when the swimmers escape throughout the pores (Fig. 1C,D). The dark color of the full-grown cysts is due to the dark body of the swimmers. The exit of swimmers from the cysts occurs naturally, but can be enhanced experimentally by addition of freshwater (20% of volume). These enhancements of germination are probably related to osmotic changes affecting the disruption of the membrane occluding the pores. A few minutes (4-10 minutes) before their exit, the swimmers begin to

move inside the parasite cyst and subsequently escape through the pores of the cyst wall. The escape of the swimmers from the parasite cyst lasts 3-7 minutes.

A droplet of unknown nature, about 8 µm diameter, remains inside the parasite cyst (Fig. 1c,d). Counts of swimmers escaped from a single parasite cyst showed numbers between 100 and 400. Occasionally some of the swimmers were unable to find the pores of the cyst wall and died in few minutes. Once outside the cysts swimmers moved with the long flagellum in front, and rotated along their axes. Swimmers accumulated near the surface of the culture vessels. They stopped their movement, and died few minutes later, when unable to infect a new host. The parasite cysts adhered easily to culture vessel surfaces, and also aggregated to form clusters of cysts (Fig. 1f).

Use of the parasite as control agent of harmful algal blooms

Several organisms, including viruses, bacteria, dinoflagellates, euglenozoa, fungi and trematodes, have been described as dinoflagellate parasites [3]. However, until now the only described parasite of *Alexandrium* species is *Amoebophyra ceratii* [4]. *A. ceratii* showed low infective rates (maximum percentage of infection 32% in *A. catenella*), and its use as a biological control agent was considered unacceptable [5]. The parasite studied in the present work showed a much higher percentage of infection among the motile host population. Within seven days after inoculation of the parasite in dinoflagellate cultures, values of infection ranged from 92.2% to 100% in *A. catenella* and from 99.8% to 99.9% in *A. minutum*. The "di-

ablillo parasite" also proved able to infect six more dinoflagellate species, but did not infect other phytoplankton groups (Table 1). These results show the selectivity of the parasite within the phytoplanktonic community. One particular case seems to be the dinoflagellate *A. taylori*, which remained resistant to infection after several attempts. This species, belonging to the subgenus *Gessnerium*, differs from the other *Alexandrium* species employed in the sense of daily formation of temporary cysts [6].

The capacities of this new "diablillo parasite", including the relatively rapid development (about 48 hours to maturity) of hundreds of new parasites per infected host, opens new perspectives for controlling blooms of harmful dinoflagellates in the natural environment. It can be expected that the effectiveness of this parasite in natural environments will require high cell densities of sensitive hosts, localized blooms, and little renovation of the water. Recurrent *Alexandrium* blooms commonly occur in semi-enclosed coastal water and these sites are thus ideal candidates. One feature of the "diablillo parasite" is that it only infected motile cells, and not the quiet cell stages of the hosts, present as temporary and resting cysts. This will present difficulties for the total destruction of the harmful algae populations in natural environments. However, this limitation of the infective potential is considered positive, since it prevents major changes in the species composition of the natural phytoplankton community. The possibility to culture the parasite on non-toxic and widespread dinoflagellate hosts (as *G. sanguineum* and *S. trochoidea*) could facilitate its use and protect

against the introduction of toxic species in different geographic areas.

Research in progress

Cooperative research is in course with Dr. Malte Elbrächter and Dr. Michael Schweikert to reveal the taxonomical position of the parasite by transmission electron microscopy and with Ms. Beatriz Díez and Dr. Carles Pedrós-Alió to determine its affiliation by analysis of 18s ribosomal sequence.

Acknowledgements

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The pattern of human respiratory syndrome in Wellington Harbour tracked well with those reported on the open coast around Wairarapa and Hawke Bay. In Wellington Harbour, 87 people reported suffering from respiratory illness; beach-goers, swimmers, and wind-surfers all complained of a dry cough, a severe sore throat (like swallowing razor blades), running nose, and skin and eye irritations. Furthermore, hatchery workers and divers working for the National Institute of Water and Atmospheric Research (NIWA) complained among other symptoms also of severe headaches, and a facial sun-burnt sensation.

During the period from 16 February and 30 March 1998, brine shrimps and all phytoplankton cultures, kept at the NIWA's hatchery facilities, were the first to be affected. Cultures, maintained in filtered seawater which was sourced from the harbour during the outbreak, died in a matter of days. Subsequently, sea horses, juvenile and large turbot, and cockle spat cultured at the hatchery, also crashed.

The unprecedented bloom that wreaked havoc in Wellington Harbour was found to be dominated by an undescribed *Gymnodinium* sp. (cell concentration 33.3 million cells per litre). The morphological characters of this new species are more like the Japanese *Gym-*

nodinium mikimotoi than any other species. The cell is dorso-ventrally flattened and has very short expression of the apical groove on the ventral surface of the epicone (Fig. 2). A full description of this new species has been made by the author and is now in press (*Phycologia* 38(5)).

One of the notable features of the 1998 Wellington Harbour bloom was the build-up of extensive sea-foam. Apparently the dissolved organic substances released at the end of the bloom by both the new Wellington *Gymnodinium* sp. and marine organisms killed by toxins were the source of this sea-foam accumulation in the harbour. The foam persisted for several weeks in the semi-

Fig. 2. Scanning electron micrograph of the new Wellington Harbour *Gymnodinium* sp.

enclosed harbour between March and early May 1998.

During this toxic outbreak, mussels growing on NIWA's hatchery rafts in Wellington Harbour were collected for toxicity tests. Mouse bioassay tests conducted by Environmental Sciences Research showed positive results; mice died very quickly in 4-6 minutes. At first it was thought that a fast-action, lipid-soluble toxin, similar to the gymnodimine that was isolated from the 1994 toxic shellfish outbreak around Foveaux Strait, New Zealand, was responsible for the mice kills. But, unlike gymnodimine, the Wellington toxin is extractable with ether. Further chemical analysis is currently being undertaken.

The Wellington Harbour toxin is stable in both alkaline and acidic conditions, but is not stable in weak acid. The instability of this toxin in weak acid makes it less likely to pose any human health risk when it is eaten. It is also thermally unstable as when heated to 100°C it lost most of its toxicity. But a certain level of toxicity was maintained, even though boiled for 30 minutes. This toxin is also characterised as being highly oxidisable, and therefore can be destroyed by ozonation. During the outbreak, ozone was used to get rid filtered seawater of toxins in NIWA's hatchery facilities before being used for cultures.

Several cultures of the new Wellington *Gymnodinium* sp. from the harbour were developed during the toxic episode. A wide range of marine organisms were tested with these newly developed *Gymnodinium* cultures. Brine shrimps, abalone larvae (Fig. 4), tintinnids, amphipods, barnacle nauplii, polychaete worms, lobster larvae (phyllosoma stage I and III), and turbot fish exposed to toxins produced by the new Wellington *Gymnodinium* sp. were all being killed.

Toxins produced by *Gymnodinium* sp. also lysed cells of naked nanoflagellates (including the Japanese *G. mikimotoi*, and the European *G. cf. mikimotoi*), and killed thecate dinoflagellates (including

Alexandrium minutum and *Prorocentrum lima*) and diatoms.

The most notable of all is that seaweeds were killed when exposed to the toxins produced by this new Wellington Harbour *Gymnodinium* sp., particularly the common brown seaweed, *Macrocystis pyrifera* found in the harbour. In laboratory tests, when *Macrocystis pyrifera* was introduced to the culture of *Gymnodinium* sp., the soft, leafy part of this seaweed collapsed and fell apart in 24 to

Fig. 3. Abalone larva was killed when introduced to the culture of the new, toxic, Wellington Harbour *Gymnodinium* sp.; membrane surrounding the velum started to disintegrate, and cells (arrowheads) within the larva were being discharged from the dead animal.

48 hours. This confirmed the earlier observations of dead *Macrocystis pyrifera* (up to 75% of seaweed cover) during the toxic outbreak in Wellington Harbour.

It is thus very clear that the new Wellington Harbour *Gymnodinium* sp. is extremely toxic to a wide range of marine invertebrates, vertebrates, microalgae and macroalgae. This is consistent with observations made in the harbour during the toxic outbreak. Impacts of this new *Gymnodinium* sp. on marine life certainly are more severe than those caused by *G. mikimotoi* from Japan, *G. breve* from the Atlantic coast of the U.S.A., *G. cf. mikimotoi* from Western Europe, and *G. galatheanum* from the North Sea. In terms of impacts of airborne and waterborne toxins on humans, the Wellington Harbour *Gymnodinium* sp. toxin is pretty much like those of *G. breve* Davis from the Atlantic coast of the U.S.A. and a *Gymnodinium* sp. recently reported from South Africa.

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Fig. 1. Locations where toxic outbreaks and respiratory syndromes (shaded) were reported on the east coast and southern part of North Island, New Zealand.

◆ Chile

Fish kill in Chile associated with bloom of *Gymnodinium* sp.

Fig. 1a

The event

A large-scale fish kill developed in waters around Chiloë, Xth Region, Chile, during March and April 1999 (Fig. 1). The first kills reported were of abalone and salmon from marine farms near Quellon on 13 March, associated with patches of brown water ("marea café"). The coloured patches were sharply delimited. The following days air-borne observations showed, in a first phase, the presence of discrete patches accompanied by mortality of salmon in fish-farms on the eastern coast of the island of Chiloë. Kills of molluscs and sipunculids were also reported. The movement of the patches, northwards in the inland sea, appeared to follow the currents. The presence of coloured water in the northern sector of the island (Chacao Channel) as well as mortalities of worms, molluscs and sipunculids, were observed on 12 March. This phenomenon developed during a period when Neap Tides and unusually sunny weather combined. The period of Spring Tides from 27 March contributed to attenuate the blooms. Subsequently, the coloured water presented a more diffuse aspect, and fish kills were reported only when Spring Tides returned around the 9 April.

Examination of water samples revealed that a *Gymnodinium* sp. com-

prised 99.9% of the population, the density of which reached 8 to 9 million cells per litre in coloured patches. The alga is sensitive to light: in the presence of clouds and in the dark, it diffuses down into the water column, and the maximum cell concentration is found around 10 m. Sunshine favours its migration to the surface, where it forms discrete patches with an exponential vertical distribution.

Many factors suggest that this bloom was of oceanic origin: within a phytoplankton-monitoring program, no cell resembling this species had been observed in the area previously. The first cells counted (10 cells/ml) were in samples from oceanic coastal waters in late February (Austral summer). One possible cause of the event could be the current climate anomaly for the last 14 months in the area, with a drought and strong sunshine. It has resulted in temperatures, 15°C, 1.5°C higher than normal in the area. Furthermore, because of smaller than usual inputs of fresh-water run-off, oceanic waters (33 g/l) penetrate more easily bringing with them phytoplankton species normally found only in more oceanic coastal waters. The presence of *Gymnodinium* sp. appears strongly associated with the frontal structure of water masses in this area, and the arrival of a water mass of salinity 30 g/l is likely to have contributed to the disappearance of the alga within 24 h in the area of Quemchi.

Among the consequences of this bloom, it is important to mention a large mortality of salmon. It constitutes a severe loss for the farmers concerned. The relationship between the mortalities of marine animals and the presence of coloured water was first established in salmon-farms. The animals affected presented abundant mucus around their gills.

The species

The algal cells were very similar to the genus *Gymnodinium*, approximately 30 µm wide, with a large nucleus (10 µm) located opposite the apical extremity. Numerous small chloroplasts were visible (Fig.2). A few small cells looking like chlorophytes (1-2 µm) were also observed in fresh samples.

After storage in culture of the *Gym-*

nodium sp. samples from the coloured patches, smaller cells (10-15 µm) appeared. The large proved to be particularly fragile, and up till now, this has prevented their being transported live to Denmark for identification by J. Larsen.

Some of the properties of this species have been studied during the bloom, and they resemble those of other known species of ichthyotoxic *Gymnodinium*.

The haemolytic property: This allows one of the modes of action of the toxin (lysis) to be investigated, and it permits this toxicity to be related to a minimum concentration of algae. Freshly pre-

Fig. 2. Photo by M. Seguel, IFOP, Chile

served samples, taken from coloured water patches, as well as a culture grown in the laboratory in f/2 medium, were tested according to the usual protocol, on human red blood cells (RBCs). The results showed strong haemolytic activity in all cases, apparent after 30 minutes incubation at 18°C, with samples corresponding to a density of 4000 cells/ml. The test carried out on diluted samples showed that a concentration of 250 cells/ml showed a still non-negligible activity (18% haemolysis in an RBC suspension of 40 million/ml).

The allelopathic property: it reveals the presence of an ectocrine secreted by the algal cell, and may explain the almost monospecific nature of the blooms. Water from samples tested previously, from which the *Gymnodinium*

Fig. 1b

cells had been removed by gravity filtration through Whatman GF/F filters, were then sterilised by 0.22- μ m filtration. In order to extract any allelopathic substances, an aliquot of water was passed through Sep-Pak C18 and Florisil (Waters) cartridges. After enrichment in f/2 medium, the fractionated samples were respectively seeded using two stocks of the alga isolated in this region of Chile. The results showed that development of diatoms was totally inhibited by water from the sample having contained *Gymnodinium* sp., but that growth of a culture of *Alexandrium catenella* was practically unaffected.

This phenomenon illustrates the importance of the climatic situation and the physical oceanographic conditions in the process of bloom dynamics. High temperatures and strong sunshine, "in-oculation" currents and the stratification of water columns are probably some of

the factors responsible in this case. The biology of the species in question completes the factors controlling bloom dynamics. In producing substances with properties allelopathic to other species, this alga limits their development, and itself develops profusely. The presence of either the same substances or of other biologically active products also derived from the metabolism of the alga present at high concentration, leads to the serious impacts observed on marine organisms sensitive to these substances.

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◆ International

APEC Red Tide/HAB Project Enters Final Year

In past newsletters, the APEC Red Tide/HAB Project has been described. This project represents an effort to coordinate monitoring and management of HABs within the 21 APEC (Asia Pacific Economic Cooperation) economies in order to facilitate a free flow of goods and services, and in particular, shellfish and fish products potentially contaminated with algal toxins. These efforts are similar in some ways to activities within the European Union, which has also been establishing import and export guidelines.

The Red Tide/HAB project structure is composed of a Program Steering Committee, which provides general oversight, and two Task Teams – a Task Team on Algal Biotoxin Regulations and a Task Team on Analytical Methods and Standards. The former is chaired by Sherwood Hall and the latter by Mike Quilliam. The project Overseer is Rod Forbes of Canada.

The latest round of APEC meetings took place during the conference on Harmful Algae Management and Mitigation (HAMM) which took place in Subic Bay, Philippines in May, 1999. One of the major activities of the Task Teams during the last year has been the organization and convening of this con-

ference, which was co-sponsored by the IOC and received additional support from institutions in the Philippines, Chinese Taipei and the United States. The Task Teams have also been polling individual economies on their action limits for HAB toxins, and have been working towards establishing "performance criteria" for each of the algal toxins, rather than specifying a specific method which must be adhered to by all. The Analytical Methods and Standards Task Team is preparing summary tables of the many different methods that can be used for algal toxin detection and measurements, providing guidance on their suitability with respect to the proposed performance criteria. In addition, a proposal is being submitted to obtain external funding for a program which will address the needs for analytical standards as well as for an inter-calibration exercise involving laboratories within the APEC economies.

In a departure from the approach taken by the European Union, APEC does not feel it is feasible to have a single Regional Reference Laboratory as a central node in a network of National Reference Laboratories. Instead, two networks are envisioned both voluntary. The first is a Group of Authorities on

Algal Biotoxin Regulations. This group would comprise individuals and institutions responsible for management of seafood product safety and trade. It would meet periodically, but would also communicate frequently over the Internet to insure that high level attention is given to issues related to the certification of seafood potentially affected by algal toxins. The second network, a Group of Experts on Analytical Methods, could assist in resolving disputes or provide advice to individual APEC economies in need of assistance. In the coming months, individuals and agencies who will become part of these two networks will be identified both by Task Team members and by individual APEC economies through formal invitations for nomination. This is one area where we hope that the project can influence activities and policies within the APEC economies long after it terminates at the end of this next year.

Another activity that will be undertaken during the intercession will be the establishment of an APEC Web page for this project. In addition to providing access to a number of the reports and general information that is generated, the Web page will also link to many sites throughout the world where useful pub-

lic education information is available on HABs. With the help of many in our HAB community, Georgina Lembeye compiled leaflets, brochures, fax sheets, and other sources of general information used in countries world wide to communicate the facts and dangers of HABs.

This compilation is very useful, but it was felt that it would be easier to disseminate this type of information through a Web page which links to existing sites where this information is available.

Overall, the APEC Red Tide Project is proceeding well, and will finish its

deliberations within a year. The growing restrictions on trade involving seafood products potentially contaminated with algal toxins underscores the importance of these types of activities.

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◆ Italy

Toxicity of *Prymnesium* in the shallow lake of Massaciuccoli (Migliarino-San Rossore- Massaciuccoli Regional Park -Pisa-Tuscany)

In January 1999 a *Prymnesium* sp. (presumably *P. patelliferum*) bloom occurred with 18000 cells/ml; it caused an extensive fish mortality in the lake of Massaciuccoli (1). This lake is connected to the sea, and has brackish waters with a range of Cl⁻ of 700-2000 mg/l, its average depth is 2,5 m, volume 11000 m³, area 6,8 km². It is situated in a wetland zone below sea level (- 0,80 + 0,35 m). From 1930 the area around the lake has been reclaimed as agriculture land. Subsequently, the trophic conditions and anthropogenic influences in the area have led to increased eutrophication, and a progressive loss of submerged macrophytes in favour of microalgae growth. The increased amounts of phytoplankton revealed the presence of *Prymnesium* sp., which caused fish mortality in 1972 (2) and in later years. Usually the blooms of *Prymnesium* have taken place during the winter period (December-March), preceding cyanobacterial blooms (*Lyngbya* spp., *Microcystis* spp.), when the water temperature is 7-8 °C. The *Prymnesium* toxins kill fishes and *Daphnia magna*, but not Copepoda such as *Cyclops*.

Mortality of Cladocera alters the trophic web, and throws the ecosystem out of balance (3). Toxicity of *Prymnesium* is demonstrated in the laboratory by bioassays using *Carassius auratus* (4) which die within 24 hours, and *Daphnia magna* which die within 4 days. Generally the toxicity occurs with concentrations of 10000 cells/ml. Electronic microscopy, in co-operation with the Department of Botany of Florence University has shown that the species is *Prymnesium patelliferum*.

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◆ Review

Cortes Atamirano, R.

LAS MAREAS ROJAS

This is a book written in Spanish about red tides that includes all of the harmful algae that cause or do not cause discoloration of sea water. The section on toxic events is confined mostly to the coastal region of Mexico and serves as a useful reference for other coastal regions. The book covers a range of aspects related to red tides, from the dynamics of formation to suggestions for prevention of the toxic effects of harmful episodes at the national and international level. The opening chapter briefly describes the dynamics of formation, maintenance and disappearance of red tides. Three chapters follow on experimental methods of monitoring and a description and summary of toxic episodes in Mexican and associated waters and causal species. A series of diagrams are included to aid identification. The next four chapters are dedicated to toxicology and start with a description of the most frequent toxins (PSP, DSP, NSP, ASP) and their effects. It then describes human symptoms contracted from ingestion of the four types of toxin. The next two chapters are dedicated to methodological aspects of toxin concentration determination by rat bioassay and HPLC. The author then places everything into a series of research programmes for the prevention of the toxic effects of red tides at the National and International level and in the last chapter includes suggestions of how this may be achieved. Each chapter has a relevant bibliography section and to complement this there is a more extensive list of useful titles compiled as an appendix. A series of other appendices are included which relate to the diverse themes of the book and of most interest is the list of micro-algal species responsible for toxic red tides. In this list there

are series of keys, which allow the identification of various species, associated aspects such as toxin types, and effects on human health. This book is very useful to Spanish readers who work in the monitoring and management of coastal waters.

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Identification Service

The IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae, Copenhagen, and the Asian Natural Environmental Science Center offers an identification service. If you have problems with identification of harmful algal species, the Centres may assist you. You should send samples to one of the two addresses given below. It should be noted that this assistance is not given for routine identification/monitoring of samples, but applies to particularly difficult species, or to

species that require special techniques e.g. electron microscopy, for identification.

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Asian Environmental Science Center, The University of Tokyo, Att.: Dr. Y. Fukuyo, Yayoi 1-1-1, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo 113, Japan.

IOC-IEO-AECI III Course on Toxic Microalgae and Marine Phycotoxins

The third training course on toxic microalgae and marine phycotoxins organized by the IOC-IEO Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae was held from 1st to 17th of June 1999, at the Instituto Español de Oceanografía (IEO) in Vigo, Spain. This course is part of the Harmful Algal Bloom Programme of IOC and is funded by the IOC, the Agencia Española de Cooperación Internacional (AECI) and the IEO. Twelve scientists from different

developing countries participated in the course (Argentina, Angola, Brazil, Colombia, Costa Rica, Cuba, Chile, Ecuador, Guatemala, Haiti, Mexico and Venezuela). Lecturers were given by personnel from the IEO, The Instituto de Investigaciones Mariñas (Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas), The European Union Reference Laboratory on Marine Biotoxins, Centro de Control da Calidade do Medio Mariño (Xunta de Galicia), ANFACO-

CECOPESCA, the Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae, plus other guest lecturers from three Spanish Universities (Oviedo, Vigo and Santiago).

Apart from a general introduction to harmful microalgae, the practical training part of the course was focussed on four different aspects of toxic phytoplankton: Toxin determination, Establishment of algal cultures (collections and large-scale), Taxonomy, and Benthic harmful microalgae. At a seminar all participants made a presentation describing HAB research and management related activities in their respective countries. Time was also available for the participants to work on their own plankton samples. The laboratory training was complemented with field sampling methodologies and visits to the local research laboratories working with HAB.

The general impression of the outcome of the course was very positive among both trainees and lecturers, and valuable contacts for future collaboration were established among the participants. This IOC training course is organized annually, and additional information can be requested from the IOC-IEO Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae at fax +34-986-492003 or e-mail: vigohab@vi.ieo.es.

For general information on IOC Training Courses on HAB please consult <http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/train.htm>

◆ China

Phaeocystis bloom in southeast China coastal water 1997

Fig.1. *Phaeocystis globosa* cells in gelatinous colonies

From beginning of October to late December 1997, one intensive bloom along the coast of Fujian and Guangdong provinces occurred. This huge bloom lasted about two months. The causative species was identified as *Phaeocystis globosa* Scherffel (Fig.1). The spherical colonies in nonmotile stage of cells are about 1.5 to 3mm in diameter. Cells are evenly distributed along the surface of the colony. The gelatinous colonies with or without lobes

and distributive patterns of cells in the colony stage are two distinctive characteristics for separating *Phaeocystis pouchetii* and *Phaeocystis globosa*. According to this, the bloom species in southeast China coastal waters is not *Phaeocystis pouchetii* (Hariot) Lagerheim but *Phaeocystis globosa* Scherffel. This species is also recorded in the coastal waters of Hainan province and Hong Kong. The discoloration caused by this species during the late autumn and early winter was detected by

SeaWiFS imagery (Fig.2). The bloom caused severe mortality of caged-fish. An estimated 60 000 tons of fish were killed. The direct loss was 66 million Chinese Yuan (about 8 million US dollars).

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Fig.2 SeaWiFS image of *P. globosa* bloom on 13th of November 1997 (arrows)

◆ Mexico

National HAB Training Course in Mexico. Monitoring Program Launched Early 1999

The first report of red tides impacting human health in Mexico was in the XIX century, and led to coughing and cutaneous rashes in people living near the Veracruz coast, as well as mass fish mortalities [1]. But previously, Brongersma-Sanders [2], had reported fish mortalities as "very frequent" since 1797 in the Gulf of Mexico. From that time on, there were sporadic reports until 1979, when the first documented casualty due to Paralytic Shellfish Poisoning (PSP) occurred near Mazatlan Bay, Sinaloa [3,4]. Since then, continuous observation of the area has been maintained [5], and later extended to Bacochibampo Bay farther north in Sonora State.

Regarding the presence and distribution of Marine Biotoxins in Mexico, until now we have positively identified events caused by saxitoxins (PSP), brevetoxins (NSP), domoic acid (ASP), ciguatoxins (CFP) and cyanobacteria hepatotoxins [6]. In addition, we are aware of the presence of okadaic acid and dinophysistoxin-1 (DSP) in shellfish, but without any directly related events so far [7].

This information was gathered in spite of the absence of a coordinated network for monitoring red-tide events. Furthermore, there was a lack of properly trained individuals to record the ecological and toxicological aspects of

these phenomena. Thus, it was decided that one of the main goals was to train individuals to evaluate and manage red-tides. These efforts started during the First Training Course "Evaluation and

Prevention of Red Tide Effects in Mexico", held in Mazatlan, Sinaloa, in May 28-31, 1996. This course, organized by the Plankton Laboratory (Mazatlan Station-UNAM), and attended by nine trainees, was given by specialists from the Biotoxins Laboratory (CIBNOR), National Fisheries Institute (SEMARNAP), Invertebrates Laboratory (UNAM), and the Phytoplankton and Productivity Laboratory (ICMyL-UNAM), with broad experience in the biology, taxonomy and toxicology of harmful algae. Toxicological training ranged from mouse bioassays to HPLC methods for the determination of marine biotoxins. As a by-product of this course, a manual was prepared which was finally published in 1998 [8].

In April, 1997, the Central Laboratory of Chemistry and Aquatic Toxicology (INP-SEMARNAP), the Regional Fisheries Research Center and 5 Regional Institutes from the State of Veracruz, hosted the Second Training Course on Red Tides, with 25 trainees. The same year (March, 1997), the National Shellfish Sanitary Program held a Training Course in Acapulco, Guerrero, where the main subject was the mouse bioassay for PSP toxins; it was restricted to their own local personnel.

Recently, from 23-26 November, 1998, a joint venture of CIBNOR, UECyM-SEP, ICMYL-UNAM and PROFEPA, led to the Third National Training Course on the Evaluation and Prevention of the Effects of Marine Biotoxins and Red Tides in Mexico. This course was held at CIBNOR premises in La Paz, B.C.S. There were twenty five attendants from eleven Mexican States. Each trainee has the opportunity to study samples of all species that produce red tides in Mexico (dinoflagellates, diatoms and cyanobacteria). Additionally, biology and ecology of the organisms, monitoring tools, remote sensing, toxicology and qualitative and quantitative determination of algal toxins were broadly discussed by participants.

Nowdays, the facilities of CETMARs and ITMARs, medium and high level educational institutes respectively, coordinated by Unit of Education, Science and Technology of the Sea-Education Ministry (UECyTM-SEP) which are spread all along the coasts of Mexico, and the Monitoring and Research Program developed by the Biotoxins Laboratory at CIBNOR, have merged efforts to foster a network for the permanent study of red-tides. The Education

Ministry have provided the funds to run local monitoring activities in each locality, as well as the necessary equipment. The seven institutes on the Pacific coast received new microscopes, cell culturing equipment and toxin extraction equipment, and the rest of the institutions will be supplied with the necessary equipment within the next two years.

These goals would not have been accomplished without the sponsorship of IOC via scholarships to Roberto Cortes Altamirano (to attend the Training Course in Vigo, Spain) and Arturo P. Sierra-Beltran (to attend Training Courses in Jena, Germany and Helsingor, Denmark). We hope to link up with other initiatives in the IOCARIBE region in the near future, and to participate actively in the Harmful Algae Project in the Caribbean (ANCA). We are now organizing the First IOCARIBE Training Course on Harmful Algae to be carried out in November 1999 at CIBNOR premises in La Paz, B.C.S., Mexico.

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ICES- IOC Working Group on Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics

The ICES- IOC Working Group on Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics (WGHABD) was established in 1994. One aim of the Working Group is to outline the various physical, chemical and biological interactions associated to harmful algal blooms (HAB) and to define the main gaps in research.

An important task of WGHABD is to collect up-to-date information about HAB occurrences. This information maintained as a HAB database by the IOC Communication Center on HAB in Vigo, and summarized as decadal maps in the ICES web-page (<http://www.ices.dk/status/status.htm>).

The next meeting of the Working Group will be held in Barcelona, Spain, from 20 to 24 March 2000.

The IOC and ICES are encouraging scientists from outside the North Atlantic to join the Working Group. If you are interested you can get more information on the Working Group at <http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/act6.htm> or by contacting the Chair of the Working Group Dr. Kaisa Kononen at kaisa.kononen@nessling.fi. The IOC has a limited number of grants for scientists from developing countries to participate. If you are interested you should contact Henrik Enevoldsen (hab.ioc@unesco.org) at the IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae with a description of your background and interest in the activities of the Working Group.

Since August 1994 the ASEAN-Canada Cooperative Programme on Marine Science has sponsored the South East Asian Harmful Algae Bulletin, SEAHAB. Unfortunately funding for this has come to an end. While SEAHAB is investigating ways and means to continue, Harmful Algae News has agreed temporarily to include a section for SEAHAB.

If you are interested in supporting the survival of SEAHAB please contact the Editor, Dr. Rhodora V. Azanza, Ph.D., Marine Science Institute, CS, University of the Philippines, Diliman, Quezon City 1101, Philippines, Tel: (632) 9215967/9223959, Fax: (632) 9215967, Email: rhod@msi01.cs.upd.edu.ph

The articles which follows hereafter were submitted via SEAHAB.

◆ Philippines

Ciguatera Fish Poisoning: Occurrence and Research in the Philippines

Ciguatera Fish Poisoning is a newly known type of algal biotoxin poisoning in the Philippines. The presence of causative organisms such as *Prorocentrum lima*, *Prorocentrum concavum* and *Ostreopsis siamensis* was first observed by Fukuyo (pers. comm.) in Cebu and Iloilo in 1994. Azanza and Taylor also observed the presence of ciguatera causing organisms in the seaweeds, *Jania* spp. and *Laurencia* spp. collected from White Island, Camiguin, Philippines in 1995.

Recently, a "Ciguatera Fish Poisoning" event was reported in Romblon, Philippines in September 1997. There were 35 cases of fish poisoning from this date until February 1998 and out of these cases, 25 showed symptoms that fit very closely those of Ciguatera Fish Poisoning while 3 other cases showed symptoms of palytoxin poisoning. The remaining cases showed symptoms not related to the abovementioned poisonings. Samples of the vector fish *Lethrinus* sp. locally called "dugso" were sent to Dr. Richard Lewis of the University

of Queensland, Australia and Dr. Fran Van Dolah of the US. National Marine Fisheries Services, Charleston for analysis. Dr. Allan Dionisio of the Philippine General Hospital and Dr. Teresa Castillo of the Philippines' Department of Health visited the site in February 1998 and conducted seminars on the detection of symptoms of ciguatera poisoning to local medical officers. Awareness on this kind of poisoning had increased especially in Cajidiosan, Romblon.

At present, the Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources and the University of the Philippines in the Visayas are conducting serial monitoring of fish and dinoflagellates from selected sites in Romblon in relation to ciguatera fish poisoning. Medical doctors in Romblon have been provided by Drs. Dionisio and Castillo with a questionnaire relevant to the epidemiology of this type of poisoning.

Rhodora V. Azanza & Lilibeth N. Miranda, Marine Science Institute, University of the Philippines

◆ Australia

IAEA Regional Training Workshop on Harmful Algae

The International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) sponsored a Regional Harmful Algal Blooms Training Workshop on Sedimentation and Algal Cysts Studies which was held in Hobart/Sydney, Australia 5-10 July 1999 in line with its regional project on the "Application of Nuclear Techniques to address specific red tide (harmful algal blooms) concerns." This regional project was developed based on the National IAEA program of the Philippines with almost the same title. The training program was composed of two parts. The first part was on algae identification held at the Department of Plant Science, University of Tasmania. The second part was on field sampling and radiometric dating of sediments at the Environmental Radiochemistry Laboratory, Australian Nuclear Science and Technology Organization (ANSTO).

The workshop participants were familiarized with the techniques on Radiometric dating using Polonium-210, Radium-226 and Lead-210 by alpha and gamma spectrometry analysis.

There were 16 participants from China, Indonesia, Malaysia, Pakistan, the Philippines, Thailand and Vietnam. Dr. Gustaff Hallegraeff of the University of Tasmania and Dr. Hendrik Heijnis of the Environmental Radiochemistry group of the Environment Division, ANSTO, headed the team of lecturers. Dr. Heijnis is the IAEA/RCA/UNDP technical expert on the application of Nuclear Techniques to address specific red tide (harmful algal blooms) concerns, i.e. use of radio labeling for dating of sediments. Dr. G. Hallegraeff was in charge of the training on isolation and identification of algal cysts from the sediments.

Rhodora V. Azanza, Ph.D. & Lilibeth N. Miranda, Marine Science Institute, University of the Philippines, 1101 Diliman Quezon City

◆ International

First Conference on Harmful Algae Management and Mitigation

The first Conference on Harmful Algae Management & Mitigation (HAMM) was successfully chaired by Dr. Sherwood Hall of the United States Food and Drug Administration (USFDA) and hosted by the Marine Science Institute (MSI) of the University of the Philippines on 10-14 May 1999 at Crown Peak Gardens Hotel, Subic Bay, Philippines.

Dr. Rhodora V. Azanza of MSI and Mr. Robert Jara of the Department of Environment and Natural Resources served as the co-chairmen of the Local Organizing Committee. The Conference was sponsored and held under the auspices of the Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC) and the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC), and co-sponsored by the Government of the Republic of the Philippines (University of the Philippines= Marine Science Institute, Department of Agriculture-Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources, Department of Science and Technology-Philippine Council for Aquatic and Marine Research and Development and the National Research Council of the Philippines), Environmental Protection Administration of Chinese-Taipei, National Taiwan University (Chinese-Taipei), Environmental Protection Agency of the United States of America and the Interstate Shellfish Sanitation Conference.

The conference aimed to facilitate the management and mitigation of the impacts of harmful algal blooms to enhance sustainable use of marine resources. The primary goal of this Conference was to share and develop mechanisms for minimizing the impact of harmful algae and their toxins on human health, commerce, fisheries resources, and the marine ecosystems throughout and beyond the Asia-Pacific region.

HAMM was attended by 104 participants representing the academe, industry, and policy-makers from 25 countries (Australia, Brazil, Bulgaria, Canada, China, Chinese-Taipei, Denmark, Japan, Malaysia, Mexico, New Zealand, Peru, the Philippines, Republic of Korea, Russia, Singapore, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Thailand, Uruguay, USA, Venezuela and Vietnam). There were about 69 papers presented. The papers were categorized into six different themes, namely: (a) Organisms, Toxins, Mechanisms, (b) Economic and Social Impacts, (c) Management Options, (d) Mitigation Strategies, (e) Intergovernmental Cooperation, and (f) Management and Regulatory Compatibility.

Three workshops were held during the conference. These were a Toxin Workshop, a Plankton Workshop, and the Focus Group Work Sessions. The Toxin workshop consisted of specialized lectures on toxins and detection methods, detection method training and demonstrations and focus group discussions related to toxins and detection methods. The Plankton workshop included specialized lectures on plankton taxonomy and biology, training in taxonomy, sampling and observation and focus group discussions related to plankton. While the Focus Group Work Sessions was a discussion of issues and production of consensus text which will be assembled to form the Guidelines for HAMM.

The six Focus Group Sessions were: (a) Scope of the Problem and Impacts, (b) Monitoring Programme Structure and Design, (c) Management Support Tools, (d) Analytical Methods and Standard, (e) Environmental Control and Mitigation Strategies, and (f) Regulation and Trade.

Some of the important questions/topics addressed during the sessions were: How does one decide when a management program is justified? Is risk assessment a useful tool for managing HABs? How much should an

economy with no history of HAB problems be doing?

The discussions also focused on prudent forms of management given a lack of historical data; coordination of efforts between various government agencies; co-ordination among individual governments within biological region; industry involvement /certification programmes; the use of readily observable phenomena as indicators of HABs; effective training and education tools; incorporation of other monitoring programs; policies for the consumption of fish killed by HAB; risks to humans from direct exposure; how do current regulatory requirements impact on trade?. Major attention was also given to the cost-benefit of HAM monitoring: are regulations and effective monitoring programs a cost or good business practice? Is there value in considering the adoption of standardized or complimentary regulations among APEC economies, and how should this be done? How can importing economies improve confidence in the management programs and certification of product safety of an exporting economy? How can an exporting economy develop confidence that, if they are forthright in divulging information on shellfish toxicity in their shellfish products, importing economies will respond properly?

It is planned that there will be proceedings and potentially other products of the HAMM Conference addressing some of the above issues. Information on this will follow in coming issues of Harmful Algae News and at <http://vm.cfsan.fda.gov/~frf/sfhamm.html>. During the conference it was suggested and discussed if the HAMM Conference could be the first in a new series of conferences on HAB management and mitigation.

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◆ Vietnam

Trichodesmium erythraeum bloom

For many years scientists of the Institute of Oceanography, Nhatrang (ION), Vietnam, have been investigating the waters of Binhthuan province, Vietnam. There is a strong upwelling in the area in July-August every year, but the oceanographic conditions and the phytoplankton associations have never been studied in detail. Preliminary results indicate that diatoms, particularly *Proboscia alata*, are found in high densities during the upwelling period. Also dinoflagellates, e.g. *Noctiluca scintillans*, can sometimes be dominant.

Recently, Nguyen & Doan (1996) reported a bloom of *Trichodesmium erythraeum* in the Binhthuan waters. According to the experience of the local fishermen living in the coastal villages, this is apparently a recurrent phenomenon during the period March to July. In some cases, fish kills occur, but the reason for this is not clear. So far there has been no official reports of socio-economic problems relating to blooms of *T. erythraeum* or other phytoplankton organisms in Vietnam.

In November 1998, a cooperative research programme on harmful algal blooms, HABViet, was commenced between the IOC Science & Communication Centre on Harmful Algae, University of Copenhagen, Denmark, and the National Oceanographic Institute in Nhatrang, Vietnam. The project is sponsored by DANIDA and will survey the distribution of potentially harmful microalgae in Vietnamese waters. A sampling programme has been initiated and covers most of the Vietnamese coast (Fig. 1A) including the Binhthuan area (Fig. 1B). In the samples from 26-28 March 1999, *T. erythraeum* was recorded again. The sea was calm and the

Figure 2. Grey tide of *Trichodesmium erythraeum*

bloom discoloured the water and formed long scattered bands (Fig. 2) extending about 8 km along the coast of Tuyphong, in the Binhthuan Province. The highest cell density was at northern end of the area, near Cau Island (Fig. 1B). The samples were collected at 10-15 metres depth, the salinity of the surface layer was about 32 ppt. and the temperature of the surface and bottom water (15 m) was and 28-29°C, and 26-27°C respectively.

In the surface layer, diatoms and dinoflagellates were very few, but the composition of other phytoplankton species associat-

ed with the bloom has not been analysed in detail.

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Figure 1. (A) Map of Vietnam indicating the coastal provinces where the HABViet Project has sampling sites. (B) Area affected by grey tide.

THE IOC HARMFUL ALGAL BLOOM PROGRAMME

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New IOC HAB Homepage!

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HAB-DIR on the net again!

The International Directory of Experts In Harmful Algae and Their Effects on Fisheries and Public Health, in short HABDIR, is an international directory which lists research scientists, fisheries managers, public health officials, aquaculture professionals, physicians, and animal health specialists who are experienced in dealing with toxic and harmful algal event and their impact on fisheries and public health. The directory is intended to improve and accelerate international information exchange and rapid access to experts who can respond quickly to these outbreaks and thus help

reduce the consequences to fisheries and public health.

The first edition of this directory was published in 1990 by Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution Sea Grant program. The second edition was a cooperative effort by the U.S. Department of Commerce, U.S. NOAA National Marine Fisheries Service, U.S. Northeast Fisheries Science Center, and the IOC. The Third edition which provide the basis or the WWW version was prepared by the IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae, University of Copenhagen, Denmark.

After the introduction of the Directory to the WWW it can be currently updated and amended. The Directory is by no means comprehensive, but it is hoped that all users will help correct mistakes and encourage their colleagues to join the Directory.

<http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/data1.htm#1>

◆ International

Updated Questionnaire on Design of Harmful Algal Bloom Monitoring Systems

Harmful Algal Blooms (HAB) continues to be a problem to seafood safety and to local or regional economies. The IOC Harmful Algal Bloom Programme is endeavouring to take initiatives which help to provide a better basis for designing and implementing HAB monitoring and management systems.

A global survey was made in 1995 on how various countries had designed and implemented their HAB monitoring programmes. This first survey resulted in the publication of a report in the IOC Technical Series (No.44) summarizing the results. The report has been one of the most requested IOC publications ever since and is now out of stock. The full material from the survey is also available as a meta data base which is accessible via the IOC HAB homepage.

Almost five years have passed, many more countries or areas have now HAB monitoring systems, and many monitoring programmes have probably been modified. It has therefore been decided to update the IOC-ICES database on how harmful algae are monitored around the world.

Your assistance in up-dating, or submitting for the first time, information on HAB monitoring in your country, region, or area, is extremely valuable and the success of this initiative depends on the collaboration of national monitoring agencies.

The questionnaire can also be downloaded from <http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/data2.htm#1> and we welcome as many electronic submissions of the questionnaire as possible.

Thank you in advance for your cooperation.

IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae

Henrik Enevoldsen

Proceedings of the 7th and 8th International Conference on Harmful Algae

Are still available at a very low price. To libraries and laboratories in developing countries it is free of charge. For all others there is a 30 USD handling fee/copy.

The Spanish Institute of Oceanography, University of Tokyo, University of Copenhagen, and Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution are helping in the sale and distribution, and thanks to their support, cost is kept to a minimum.

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Future events

February 2000

HABTech 2000, A workshop on harmful algal bloom & marine biotoxin monitoring Cawthron Institute, Nelson, New Zealand, 3-5 February 2000. More details at: <http://www.cawthron.org.nz> and <http://webnz.com/nelson> Registration: People who wish to attend should register by post or E-mail at Info@cawthron.org.nz as soon as possible. If you wish to make personal contact with the organizers please e-mail, or fax (0064 3 546 9464) either: Jenny Ragg (info@cawthron.org.nz), Lesley Rhodes (Lesley@cawthron.org.nz), Lincoln Mackenzie (Lincoln@cawthron.org.nz).

February 2000

9TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON HARMFUL ALGAL BLOOMS- "HAB2000", 7-11 FEBRUARY 2000, HOBART, TASMANIA, AUSTRALIA

The HAB2000 conference will provide a broad forum for phycologists, microbiologists, toxicologists, physiologists, molecular biologists, aquatic ecologists and managers to address and exchange research findings and perspectives concerning all aspects of toxic and harmful algae, including freshwater cyanobacteria and ciguatera fish poisoning. Harmful algae and their toxins can have serious implications for human health, aquaculture, fisheries, seafood trade, tourism and the aquatic environment. These phenomena pose a growing global problem at a time when human reliance on coastal zones for food, recreation and commerce is expanding. CONFERENCE SECRETARIAT: Conference Design Pty. Ltd., PO Box 342, Sandy Bay, Tasmania 7006, Australia, Telephone: intl +61 3 62243773; Fax: intl +61 3 62243774; e-mail:

mail@cdesign.com.au CONFERENCE WEBSITE (including registration & hotel reservation forms): http://www.utas.edu.au/docs/plant_science/HAB2000/

June 2000

3RD INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MOLLUSCAN SHELLFISH SAFETY, Southampton College, Long Island University, New York, USA, 19-23 June 2000. The sessions will be dealing with shellfish biology and ecology; impacts of harmful and toxic algae; monitoring and management; health and sanitation; chemical and microbiological contamination and assessment; depuration technology; aquaculture and harvesting sites; quality assurance programmes and regulatory controls. Contact: ICMSS c/o Dr. Sandra E. Shumway, Natural Science Division, Southampton College, LIU, Southampton, NY, 11968 USA, Fax: +1 516 287 8419, E-mail: sshumway@southampton.liunet.edu

August 2000

IOC DANIDA TRAINING COURSE ON THE TAXONOMY AND BIOLOGY OF HARMFUL MARINE MICROALGAE

This two weeks training course will focus on identification and preparation techniques supplemented by lectures on different aspects of the biology of harmful algae. Teaching staff will include: Dr. Y. Fukuyo (Univ. of Tokyo), Prof. Ø. Moestrup (Univ. of Copenhagen), Dr. J. Larsen (Univ. of Copenhagen/IOC Centre). The Course is organized by the University of Copenhagen and the IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae. The course has 10 seats free-of-charge for participants from developing countries,

Literature for developing country libraries

Limited copies of the following titles are available from the IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae, Denmark (see address below), to libraries of marine science institutions in developing countries only:

- The Genus *Alexandrium* Halim (Dinoflagellata). **E. Balech, 1994.**
- Algae. An Introduction to Phycology. **C. van den Hoek et al., 1995.**
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HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

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